

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

ПОЛУЧЕНИЕ НАНОСТРУКТУРИРОВАННЫХ ВАНАДИЙОКСИДНЫХ ТОНКИХ ПЛЁНОК НА ПОВЕРХНОСТИ МЕТАЛЛОКСИДНЫХ НОСИТЕЛЯХ ПУТЁМ ТЕРМИЧЕСКОГО РАЗЛОЖЕНИЯ ВАНАДИЛЬНОГО МЕТАЛЛООРГАНИЧЕСКОГО КОМПЛЕКСА $(C_5H_5)_2V=O(THF)_5$ С ЦИКЛОПЕНТАДИЕНИЛЬНЫМИ ЛИГАНДАМИ

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PRODUCTION OF NANOSTRUCTURED VANADIUM-OXIDE THIN FILMS ON THE SURFACE OF METAL OXIDE CARRIERS BY THERMAL DECOMPOSITION OF VANADYLIC ORGANOMETALLIC COMPLEXES $(C_5H_5)_2V=O(THF)_5$ WITH CYCLOPENTADIENYL LIGANDS

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Путём термического разложения пентакистетрагидрофуранатного сольватированного ванадильного комплекса, с $(C_5H_5)_2V=O(THF)_5$, полученного гидролизом бисциклопента-диенила ванадий (III) хлорида $(C_5H_5)_2VCl$ (II) в условиях слабой основности. Получены ванадий оксидные наноструктурированные тонкие плёнки на поверхности металлоксидного носителя. Обнаружено, что при концентрации 0.1 моль/100мл растворитель (THF) с объёмом 50 мл сферической Al_2O_3 с размером 5-7 мкм носителя получена 45 нм с толщиной ванадийоксидных тонких плёнок.

ABSTRACT

By thermal decomposition pentakis of tetrahydrofuranate solvated vanadyl complex with $(C_5H_5)_2V=O(THF)_5$ produced by hydrolysis of biscyclopentadienyl of vanadium (III) chloride $(C_5H_5)_2VCl$ (II) under weak basicity vanadium oxide nanostructured thin films on the surface of metal oxide carrier were produced. It was detected that vanadium oxide thin films with thickness of 45 nm were produced at concentration 0.1 mol/100 ml solvent (THF) with capacity of 50 ml of spheric Al_2O_3 with 5-7 μm carrier.

Ключевые слова: оксид ванадия, каталитическая система, поверхность катализатора, окислительное дегидрирование, изобутан, изобутилен.

Keywords: vanadium oxide, catalyst system, catalyst surface, oxidative dehydrogenation, isobutane, isobutylene.

Relevance of the problem

The requirement of chemical industry for C_2-C_4 olefins continuously grows, and the existing capacities can be insufficient [1].

At the same time among C_2-C_4 olefins the most flexible is C_4 – isobutylene [2], which at present it is used as a monomer for producing polyisobutylene, butyl rubber raw materials for the and production of methyl acrylate and other important chemical products [3].

Presently in industry isobutylene is produced by dehydrogenation of isobutane over chromia-alumina catalyst [4]. At the beginning of 2005 total production of isobutylene on technology [5] made more than 3 mil-

lion tonnes. It should be noted that oxidizing dehydrogenation of isobutane attracts practitioners as a potential alternative way of producing isobutylene. Unlike traditional dehydration of isobutene in the presence of an oxidizer equilibrium shifts towards isobutylene and it is an exothermic process.

Experimental part

All reactions and the yield of by-products were performed in nitrogen atmosphere.

Preparation conditions of organometallic compound of vanadium (III).

For this purpose in nitrogen atmosphere 0.5 mol or 15.7 of anhydrous VCl_3 in 50 ml of dehydrated tetrahydrofuran (THF) is dissolved, then it is cooled till $10^{\circ}C$

and NH_2Na in 50ml of n-heptane which was produced in a separate reaction between 13.2 g monocyclopentadiene (C_5H_6) and 4.6 g sodium amide, was added by portion. Deposited sodium cyclopentadienyl $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{Na}$ after decantation of heptane the whole $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{Na}$ was added into reaction mixture. After 2-hour stirring, it was stopped. Turbid solution was settled. The deposit is separated. Solution was evaporated to minimum in a volume and cooled till -10°C . In a few minutes pale blue polycrystals deposit. According to the data of elemental analysis fresh weight of a target product was 74% of its output. The compound corresponds to chemical formula $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{10}\text{VCl}\cdot 5(\text{C}_4\text{H}_8\text{O})$ in which all molecules of THF are coordinated and coordination bond of vanadium (III) THF cations. Temperatures of the beginning of decomposition $T_{n.p.}=140^\circ\text{C}$, end of decomposition $T_{k.p.}=160^\circ\text{C}$. According to thermogravimetric decomposition of compounds occurs to 130°C .

Oxidizing dehydration of isobutene of nanostructured vanadium oxide catalytic systems obtained by decomposition of organometallic catalytic compounds of vanadium (III) on metal oxide catalysts.

Formation of V_2O_3 and V_2O_5 nanostructured catalytic systems over metal oxide carrier and conversion of isobutane to isobutylene by oxidizing dehydrogenation with them.

1. Decomposition temperature on $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ carrier is $110 - 120^\circ\text{C}$, biscyclopentadienyl vanadyl pentakis tetrahydrofuranate

is absorbed from 25 g spheric Al_2O_3 which varies at the range of sizes prepared for 5-7 mm solution in 0.1mol/100ml tetrahydrofuranate THF of I complex, then it is mixed with magnetic mixer at medium rate until only traces of the compound remain in the solution.

In the next stage the solvent was decanted and separated from Al_2O_3 , the residual solvent is fully removed from the surface of Al_2O_3 at $60\text{-}70^\circ\text{C}$ temperature range. In the next stage the sample is thermally processed. Then the sample is deposited on metal oxide by thermal decomposition of $(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{V}=\text{O}\cdot(\text{THF})_5$ vanadyl complex. For this 0.01mol or 0.04271g of vanadyl complex is dissolved by the way of intensive mechani-

cal mixing in nitrogen in 100 ml of hydrated tetrahydrofuran solvent. Then 7-9 mm of spheric Al_2O_3 is added at room temperature and left for absorption. Absorption process is performed till the compound in solution is fully absorbed. In the next stage solvent (THF) is heated at the temperature range of $30\text{-}40^\circ$ and is fully removed in nitrogen medium and processed at $400\text{-}500^\circ\text{C}$.

Results

According to the literature data it was found out that it is widely used in the production of thin films and metal coatings on the basis of both organic (R^1) and carbonyl (CO) ligand compounds of transition elements [A]. First of all it is conditioned with the fact that thermal decomposition of compounds with M-R, M-C $\equiv$ O (σ and π) bond at the temperature range of $100\text{-}200^\circ\text{C}$ and are converted to thermally decomposed products by forming $\text{M}^0 < \frac{1}{2}$ (R-R) dimer organic products without any residual compounds. Metal or metal oxides separated from organic residue form metal or metal oxide layer on carrier and then can act as a more effective catalyst like systems with active center [6].

Considering the abovementioned the research work

describes the creation of nanostructured catalytic systems on Al_2O_3 using organometallic compound, the research of using them as a catalyst in the conversion of isobutane into isobutylene. For this purpose 100sm^3 of 7-9 mm spheric Al_2O_3 is added into 250 ml of three-neck flask and a solution containing 0.0427g (I) complex and dissolved in 100ml THF is added into it and mixed (~ 1.5 hour) until only traces of (I) complex remain in a solution. Then catalyst is separated from solution by decantation way in nitrogen medium and is given to furnace for thermal processing. In furnace it is mixed intensively and is left for thermal processing for 1 hour at average temperature $140\text{-}150^\circ\text{C}$. The sample is brought till room temperature and is again left for thermal processing to be fixed on the layer. For this purpose the sample is annealed in nitrogen at $180\text{-}190^\circ\text{C}$.

The catalytic system was used in the conversion of isobutane to isobutylene. Figure 1 shows the SEM view of V_2O_3 -vanadium (III) oxide thin film deposited on Al_2O_3 carrier and its elemental composition was defined.

Fig. 1. Elemental analysis and composition of SEM-substance

In SEM the thickness of V_2O_3 coating on Al_2O_3 carrier is given. Figure 1 shows the characteristic X-ray spectrum. It was confirmed that the studied dust particles consist of various size particles of aluminium oxide and vanadium oxide.

According to the results of researches it was found that 45 nm V_2O_3 coating and 100sm^3 7-9 mm spheric Al_2O_3 which was dissolved in 0.0427g/100ml THF solvent on the basis of $(C_5H_5)_2V=O \cdot (THF)_5$ vanadyl organometallic compound, were determined.

As to the formation of a structure between V_2O_3 on Al_2O_3 surface it should be first noted that when (I) complex is thermally decomposed the formation of coatings by chemical impact of $[V=O]^-$ anion radical on Al_2O_3 carrier was studied. Researches show that $[V=O]^-$ fragment with high energy forms

manganese oxide coating by migrating to Al – O bond on Al_2O_3 .

As a result it enables to form more active nanostructured catalytic system. In the work oxidative and dehydrogenation properties of $C_2 - C_4$ hydrocarbons of thin film nano-structured vanadium oxide were studied. As it was shown in $C_4 -$ isobutane sample that isobutane molecule V_2O_5 thin film catalytic system on Al_2O_3 carrier conforms to the catalytic surface morphology of isobutane in the range of 400-500°C and allows performing the process more efficiently by dehydrogenating more selectively according to the scheme.

Scheme 1. Probable mechanism of conversion process of isobutane to isobutylene.

Fig.2 shows visual and SEM spectral image of $(C_5H_5)_2V=O \cdot 5(THF)$ complex deposited on Al_2O_3 after thermal processing.

Thus, experimental results on the oxidative dehydrogenation of isobutane in the presence of vanadium-containing oxide and nanostructured catalysts are presented. The features of the structures of catalytic systems on the efficiency of their action on the activity and selectivity of the dehydrogenation process are studied. Oxidative dehydrogenation of isobutane, an industrial promising process for the preparation of isobutylene, was studied in the presence of vanadium oxide catalysts deposited on the surface of $\gamma-Al_2O_3$ by decomposition with organometallic complex compounds of vanadium (III) and (V). The catalytic effect in the target and side reactions is compared with the results of studying the characteristics of their volume and surface by X-ray diffraction, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy, temperature-programmed hydrogen reduction, and a number of others. Physicochemical method of investigation established that, depending on the initial vanadium metal complex taken, either the amount of reactive mobile oxygen increases or decreases, thereby promoting more efficient course of the oxide-reduction cycle and more stable operation of the catalyst.

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